

Introducing Itihase Hatekhari

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Interactions with Children
2023

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The brochure is a part of the IDSK-RLS project 'Revisiting the Craft of History Writing for Children (2023)'

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About the Project

The project, "Revisiting the Craft of History Writing for Children," was launched with the goal of creating a series of illustrated history books for children aged 12–14. The initiative aims to challenge existing perceptions of the past by innovatively re-exploring the histories of everyday sites, commodities, and events. In India, children's understanding of the past is often influenced by societal, communal, and national stories, notions, and symbols that they are taught to regard as inviolable. As a result, their perception of history is frequently shaped by patriarchal, majoritarian, and statist values. The project aims to introduce an alternative frame to look at history which is intersectional, factually informed yet sensitive towards multiple experiences of the past.

In 2022, three books were authored in Bengali: 'Deshbhag' by Anwesha Sengupta, 'Desh Bhasha' by Debarati Bagchi; and 'Desh Manush' by Tista Das. These works were later translated into English by Arunava Sinha and Assamese by Arup Kalita to reach a wider audience. In 2023, three more books have been published: 'Chayer Duniya' by Supurna Banerjee and Anwesha Sengupta, 'Nadir Chola' by Debarati Bagchi, and 'Juddher Nana Dik' by Santanu Sengupta. These books have also been translated into English by Arunava Sinha and into Assamese by Arup Kalita and Maitreyee Sharma.

About the Brochure

In this brochure we have collated the responses of children on the three new books of 2023. We conducted several workshops around these books where they were encouraged to draw and/or write on the themes that our books cover – i.e., war, environment, and commodity histories. At present we have more than 100 feedback – including both the illustrations and the written responses. In this brochure we have selected 20 illustrations and organized them thematically, following the topics of the three books.

It is important to flag a few points. Students who attended the physical sessions did not have the opportunity to read the books before the workshops. They listened to our readings and discussions and then wrote/drew on the basis of their own understandings and imaginations. It is also important to keep in mind the profile of the students who attended the workshops. Although we had conducted our storytelling sessions at various places, in Kolkata and its surroundings, the socio-economic background of the students almost remained similar.

On 2 October 2023, we had our first interaction with children. We spent the entire day with students of schools run by the Sanghati collective (known as Sanghati School or Solidarity School) and Anandagoshti (also known as the Saturday School). Sanghati is an initiative of the Bastibashi Sramajibi Adhikar Raksha Committee – a part of Mazdoor Adhikar

Sangharsh Abhiyan (MASA). They run five schools for slum children in five different locations in Kolkata. Underprivileged children of these slums are mostly enrolled in public schools, but free classes at Sanghati schools assist them in the learning process. Most of the teachers at Sanghati also come from these slums and they have day-jobs in the informal labour sector of the city (mason, plumber, driver etc.). They are active participants of MASA and have finished high school or college. They take classes in the evening according to a predetermined schedule. Two of the five schools operate under flyovers and three operate at rented rooms in the slums. Anandagoshthi school is conducted in the premises of the Institute of Development Studies Kolkata (IDSK). PhD students of the institute run this weekly school for children living in the adjacent slum. A total of 37 students attended the session.

The second workshop (October 8, 2023) was with the students of Batighar Pathshala, Kalighat, Kolkata. The parents of these children are primarily engaged in sex work. Some of the students' parents are daily wagers working for Government-sponsored projects operating in the so-called 'redlight areas' of South Kolkata. These students also go to regular government schools and attend Batighar Pathshala for additional assistance. Batighar Pathshala operates every day in a rented room at Kalighat. 19 students attended the session.

The third workshop (October 13, 2023) was held at Khidderpore. The majority of the students who attended this session were from local Muslim families. Their fathers work as construction workers, masons, house-painters, carpenters etc. Some of their mothers work as domestic helps in the nearby middle-class households. These students go to local schools and get free tuition in Nava Jyoti - a three-decade old charity organization. We collaborated with Nava Jyoti for this workshop. 35 students attended the session.

The fourth workshop (October 15, 2023) was organised in Piali, a small town outside Kolkata, near Canning. Here we collaborated with a local community library called Pialir Boighor. The children who come to Pialir Boighor belong to similar financial backgrounds. The fathers of the children are daily labourers working at various construction sites in the city. When the fathers do not have a job for a longer period, their mothers come to the city to work as a domestic help. 21 students attended the session.

About the Books

Chayer Duniya (The World of Tea) by Supurna Banerjee and Anwasha Sengupta

Chayer Duniya offers the history of tea – the ubiquitous household beverage of South Asia – from its origins to its present-day relevance. The book chronicles the evolution of tea production and consumption and traces its trajectory as a vital commodity in the global trade network during the 19th and 20th centuries. It also records the complexities and challenges faced by the tea industry in contemporary India. This book is an exploration of how tea has transcended its imperial origins to become an integral part of both regional and global cultures. It highlights the connections between labor, identity, economics, and the environment, to elaborate how a seemingly simple beverage has shaped the course of history in profound ways.

Nodir Chola (The Flow of the River) by Debarati Bagchi

Nadir Chola delves into the territory of environmental history, focusing on the intricate relationships between state-power, ordinary people, and rivers. The narrative covers 19-20th centuries, exploring the dynamic nature of rivers and their shifting courses in Ganga-Brahmaputra delta. It highlights the complex interplay between human intervention and natural processes. From colonial times to the postcolonial era, the book examines how states, driven by economic interests, sought to control rivers through embankments, engineering feats, and the construction of large dams. By weaving together environmental history, human stories, and ecological intricacies, the book invites children to view rivers as living entities with a rich tapestry of interactions that extend beyond geographical boundaries.

Juddher Nana Dik (Aspects of War) by Santanu Sengupta

The book explores the intricate history of warfare in South Asia emphasizing on the region of Bengal-Assam, providing children with a comprehensive exploration of the multifaceted impacts of wars on societies and individuals. In a world where war has become a pervasive presence, the book offers insights into its causes, logistics, effects, and far-reaching consequences across different facets of life. The book documents the role of ordinary people, climate and technology in shaping pre-modern and modern warfares. It also explores the ethics of war, the ideas of just war and unjust war, and instances of anti-war protests in various parts of the world. From political propaganda to environmental degradation, economic ripples, and the ways in which wars permeate various aspects of society, the book takes up several events from the history of Bengal and Assam to show how war shapes the contemporary world in numerous ways.

The Responses

Historicizing Commodity: Learning about Tea

Chandana Mandal, a school going teenager, was one of the young readers who read an early draft of the book 'Chayer Duniya' [The World of Tea]. In her written feedback, she had a pertinent point: "okay, so every commodity has a history; that I understand. But does that mean we need to know all such histories?" A comment such as this made us realize that we needed to make the book on tea more relatable to young readers. We tried to do so by continuously connecting the narrative with the contemporary conditions of the working class, exploitation of female workforce and the woes of the migrant workers. To increase the readability, we tried to use frequent anecdotes. The final printed book was discussed at Batighar Pathshala on October 8, 2023. Chandana, herself, was a student in this school and participated in this session.

At Batighar Pathshala we spent the entire day. The focus of the day was the book on tea. The day started with a puppeteering performance. The performance closely followed the book and highlighted the discovery of tea, establishment of tea gardens, and labour exploitations at tea gardens. After that we divided the students into three groups. Each group was assigned one chapter of the book. The chapter was read out to them and the group was asked to prepare one collaborative artwork based on that chapter. At the end of the day three such works were produced.

The King and the Queen

The children of this group divided themselves into two sub-groups and decided to draw two separate illustrations in the two halves of the art paper. Three of them drew the Chinese king Shennong, who, according to some Chinese fables, accidentally discovered tea. The other group drew Queen Catherine – the tea addict royalty who introduced the beverage to the British Royal Family. The chapter that they read focused on the origin stories and histories of tea. The illustrations reflect that these anecdotes and stories were easily understood by the children. While Catherine's role in bringing tea to England is a historical fact, Shennong's story is more of a fairytale. Our book mentions this difference between the two stories. The easy coexistence of these two figures, however, shows the blurred boundaries between fact and fiction in the minds of the young listeners. We hope that careful reading of the text will make them aware of this distinction.

Nirala Dida and the Researchers

This is perhaps the most interesting of all three artworks. In this work we see an elderly lady, surrounded by three men. They are standing near a hut; we can see mountains in the background and a tea garden surrounding them. The children themselves have titled the work 'Nirala Dida'. Nirala, an elderly woman, who was extensively interviewed by one of two writers of this book, features prominently in one of the chapters that talk about deteriorating conditions of plantation economy. The chapter also introduces interviews as a method to do contemporary history. This chapter was read out to this group. When we asked them who the three men surrounding Nirala were, they responded one was her relative and two others were the researchers interviewing Nirala. Including the researchers in the illustration reflects the group's attempt to engage with the more complex discussion of research methods in this chapter.

Plantation in Assam

The third group engaged with the chapter that focused on early plantations of Assam and North Bengal – how tea was discovered by Robert Bruce in Assam, how plantations were set up and the laborers were brought in were discussed. The group could not finish their work. But the unfinished work shows the hierarchies in the tea garden. We can see plantation laborers carrying tea; on the other hand, there are well-dressed Europeans and dhoti-clad Indians. The group has written Assam in the illustration. Perhaps, this means that this is a scene from a tea garden of Assam.

Our Observations

The participants took interest in the historical and ethnographic anecdotes that are there in the book. But the purpose of the book was to explain to the young readers how by closely reading the history of a commodity like tea we can learn about colonial and neo-colonial economy; how exploitations have gender and racial dimensions; how postcolonial states have failed in upholding the rights of workers; how globalization has produced new miseries. These larger questions did not interest the young participants as such. This can be for multiple reasons. Tea, perceived as a beverage of the grown-ups, perhaps did not excite them and the larger historical questions were difficult to relate to. To make the book more enjoyable we are now developing a card game.

Perceiving War

At Government Girls Degree College, Ekbalpur, Kolkata we had one story-telling session on October 13, 2023. The college is close to the dock area, and it has historical significance. During the second world war, when few Japanese air raids and bombing happened, the building was used as a relief camp for the locals. The participants in this session were school going children from the nearby areas. They also take free tuition at Nava Jyoti Academy – a charity organization run by a local philanthropist for underprivileged children. This organization, along with another non-profit organization named Know Your Neighbor, collaborated with us for this session.

Activities of the entire day focused on the book *Juddher Nana Dik*. Shruti Ghosh, a theatre artist, performed a dance-drama based on the book. Two video clippings were shown and Santanu Sengupta read out portions of the book. The children also made small presentations around the theme 'war'. After reading and discussions, the children were asked to draw anything that was related to the theme. Some of them focused on the actual warfare. Many chose to draw scenes of bombing from the sky, on ground warfare and various weapons. The first part of the book focuses on how environmental specificities of Bengal delta have shaped pre-modern and early colonial wars in this region. Some of the students chose to focus on this aspect. For some, war was deeply connected to national security and patriotism. Last, and perhaps most interesting group of illustrations focused on the mindless destructions of wars. The day ended with a small neighbourhood walk that reflected the cosmopolitan history of the locality.

Shayaan Ahmed, *class VII.*

Shayaan depicts three fighter jets bombing on houses from the sky. Since the bombing during World War II was discussed in great detail and video clips were shown, it is not surprising that many like Shayaan chose to draw scenes of bombardment.

Eram Rashid, *class VII.*

In this illustration we see a cavalryman, a man standing with a rifle and two tanks on the backdrop. There are also a few dead bodies and figures depicting commoners. In our understanding, this picture depicts changing techniques of warfare as well as the devastations caused by the war. In this way, this picture powerfully captures the themes of the book.

Gulabsha Khatoon, *class VIII*

Though this illustration apparently has no connection with war, it is related to the book. The book mentions how the river Ganga and Brahmaputra posed formidable challenges to the British ambitions to expand eastward. Developing faster and more efficient steamers finally helped them to conquer Assam and India's Northeast. The author read out this portion. The illustration depicts the advanced technology (steamer) "conquering" river.

Nafisa Khatoun, *class VI*

Nafisa has drawn a rifle in a black backdrop. Whether black symbolizes danger or evil is something that remains open to interpretation.

Priya Rajak, class VII

She has divided the page into two halves and has drawn a tree at the center. The right-hand side – bustling with color, leafy tree – is titled 'Pre-war'; the left-hand side – all gray and no leaves on the tree – is titled 'after war'. The illustration depicts the destruction of war by using the tree as a symbol.

Aqsa Shakil, class VIII

Aqsa has drawn a soldier standing with a rifle with the Indian flag in the backdrop. This shows how in her mind war is associated with protecting the country; it is a site of patriotism and valor. While this is a very common perception of war and such perception often glorifies war, our book tries to challenge this notion.

Our Observations

The participants were very interested in the topic of war. They read about wars in their books, watch movies where wars are important, play war-themed games. Therefore, war is an integral part of their universe. No one asked why they should be reading about war. Their illustrations showed three trends: some of them drew anti-war pictures and thus carried forward the core message of our book; some of them drew weapons or pictures directly related to the book; a few associated war with patriotism, national pride and territorial security.

Rivers and Us: Reflections from two workshops

We conducted two workshops focusing on the book Nodir Chola (The Flow of the River) with two separate groups of children.

Workshop at IDSK

The first workshop was held at the Institute of Development Studies Kolkata (October 2, 2023) with children of Saturday School and Sanghati School. These children belonging to the families of migrant workers, have been living in Salt Lake for quite a few years. While most of them have seen rivers while going to their ancestral villages, they do not encounter any river on a regular basis. Rivers are not integral to their lived world. Apart from the reading session with the author, the workshop also included a session with Disappearing Dialogues Collective - a platform that creatively engages with children to enhance their environmental awareness. The team from Disappearing Dialogues talked about the ecology of the East Kolkata Wetlands, that surround Salt Lake and then talked about various themes covered in the book. After the conversations, the children were divided into several groups and were asked to draw anything related to the book/theme of the day. The following artworks were produced.

River at its Source

The book discusses the course of Ganga and Brahmaputra – how they originate from the mountains and flow to the sea. The above illustration depicts a river surrounded by mountains. This is perhaps to show the river at its origin.

Controlling River

A Central theme of the book. The illustration shows how various European groups (marked by different flags) tried to control Indian rivers and fought each other in the process.

River and Livelihood

The illustration shows boats, farms, houses, and people on both sides of the river. It perhaps indicates how rivers provide livelihood and sustains civilization.

River and Livelihood 2

We see cultivators, fishermen, boats, paddy-fields, flourishing villages by the rivers. River here is a source of resources, livelihood and also a medium of communication.

River and Livelihood 3

The illustration shows how tea cultivation is happening by the side of the river. This indicates that the river is Brahmaputra and the region is Assam. A Fisherman is also visible in this illustration. In this illustration we also see factories on the right side and smoke coming out of them. Thus, the theme of pollution is introduced.

The River Border

The book discusses how rivers are used to mark India- Bangladesh border and the problems that arise from it. The above illustration is directly related to this topic.

Workshop at Piali

The second workshop was conducted at Piali on October 15 2023, a small village at the northern part of Sundarbans. We conducted this workshop at Pialir Boighar – a free public library run by Tapasi Mandal and her daughter Smritikana. Together they encourage the children of the village to read outside the syllabus. The library has 50 members now – all of them are school students. It also runs an adult education centre.

In Piali, the children we met have more direct relationships with the rivers. Many in their extended families earn their livelihoods from the rivers. They have seen the fury of the rivers during natural disasters. Coming from ecologically fragile Sundarbans, they are also acutely aware of the environmental crisis that the world is witnessing today. We see their own engagements with the rivers in their illustrations. The pictures they have drawn complicate and complement the book on river in many ways. We have selected a few of their illustrations to elaborate their relationship with the river.

Flood, Cyclone, Heavy Monsoon

The above illustration by Raju Mandal is a detailed narrative of a flood in the Sundarbans. We can see the embankment has breached, people are submerged in water, a dog and a tree are being carried away by the river.

This illustration is titled Aila of 2009. It was a severe cyclonic storm that extensively damaged Sundarbans. Shilpa Sarkar, who drew the picture, could not recall the storm herself. She was too young. But she had heard stories from others in the family: how her mother took her in the lap and went to the roof hoping water would not reach that height. During the workshop, Smritikana, who was a masters student narrated her memories of Aila – how the river embankment broke down, water was everywhere; snakes, cattle, tree everything were being carried away by the water; the description of the flood shelter; the diseases that followed the cyclone. In this illustration we see a reflection of these memories and conversations.

The illustration above is done by Sayani Sarkar, a student of class XI. She drew the library 'Pialir Boighor' and how it becomes inaccessible during the Monsoon months. Not all the roads of the village are all-weather roads. The road that connects the library to the main village centre remains submerged in water during the rainy season. It becomes very dangerous for the children to access the library, for common people living in this part of the village to access railway station and market.

Water Pollution

Though the book did not directly talk about water pollution, we did talk about it during the workshop. Paramika Gharami (class VII) chose to draw that. Her picture shows black plastic packets floating in the river.

River as Border

Swapnil Mondol (Class VI) drew Indo-Pakistan conflict over controlling the river border and riverine resources. This is one of the few illustrations done by the students of Piali that directly engaged with our book. But it is also important to mention that for children of Piali, bi-lateral conflicts over rivers are not unheard of. The Indo-Bangladesh border passes through Sundarbans and much of this border in this area is marked by river. Hence, the rivers here frequently become sites of international disputes.

Our Observations

The students attending the IDSK workshop engaged less with the book than the students of Piali. The first group of children live in urban slums and the river is something that they seldom encounter. Why should they know about history of the river? This remained a recurring question to them. For the second group, the river is central to their familiar world. They have stories to share; they are excited to learn more about the histories of the rivers they see every day. The second workshop was more dialogic, and the illustrations reflected the conversations.

CONCLUSION

Our general observation is that children are curious about their everyday habits, familiar geographies and events that are happening around them. When they can connect a history book with their present, they become interested in it and engage more deeply with it. For us, this is an important understanding. Some of the students told us that they disliked history because they did not know what was the purpose of learning about things that had happened so far back in time. But we realized that they were curious to know the backstories of the events, objects, and habits that they are familiar with. Perhaps, to produce historical consciousness among young readers, it is important to relate the past with the contemporary.

OUR TEAM

Writers

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and Santanu Sengupta

Artists

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ইতিহাসে হাতেখড়ি
চায়ের দুনিয়া
লেখা
সুপূর্ণা বানার্জী
অবেষা সেনগুপ্ত
ছবি
বজ্রিত চিত্রকর
সিদ্ধান্তমৌল্য চিত্রকর
কলকাতা, অক্টোবর ২০২৩
লেখা - সুপূর্ণা বানার্জী, অবেষা সেনগুপ্ত
সম্পাদনা - অবেষা সেনগুপ্ত, দেবারতি বাগচী
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ইতিহাসে হাতেখড়ি: যুদ্ধের নানা দিক
কলকাতা, অক্টোবর ২০২৩
লেখা - শান্তনু সেনগুপ্ত
সম্পাদনা - অবেষা সেনগুপ্ত, দেবারতি বাগচী
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লেখা - দেবারতি বাগচী
সম্পাদনা - অবেষা সেনগুপ্ত, দেবারতি বাগচী
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First History Lessons: The World of Tea
Kolkata, October 2023
Author - Supurna Banerjee and
Anwesha Sengupta
Translator - Arunava Sinha
Editor - Anwesha Sengupta,
Debarati Bagchi
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10056742>

First History Lessons: Aspects of War
Kolkata, October 2023
Author - Santanu Sengupta
Translator - Arunava Sinha
Editor - Anwesha Sengupta,
Debarati Bagchi
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10056761>

First History Lessons: The Flow of Rivers
Kolkata, October 2023
Author - Debarati Bagchi
Translator - Arunava Sinha
Editor - Anwesha Sengupta,
Debarati Bagchi
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ইতিহাসে হাতেখড়ি:
চাহব পৃথিবী
লেখা
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অবেষা সেনগুপ্ত
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